

Born's Rule $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ and Determinism

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. May 10, 2023

In (1) it is argued that a quantum particle's probability $P(x,t)$ satisfies a Nelson stochastic equation: $d/dt \text{ partial } P(x,t) + d/dx \text{ partial } (b(x,t)P(x,t)) = D d/dx d/dx \text{ partial } P$. ((1)) where $b(x,t) = \hbar/m d/dx \text{ partial } S(x,t) + 2D d/dx \text{ partial } \ln(R(x,t))$ ((2)) with $W(x,t) = \text{wavefunction} = R(x,t) \exp(i S(x,t))$. Thus both a quantum wavefunction (satisfying the Schrodinger equation) and a separate $P(x,t)$ are present. If $P(x,0) = W^*(x,0)W(x,0)$ ((3)), i.e. Born's rule, then this rule holds for later times. It is, however, suggested in (1) that if $P(x,0) \neq W^*(x,0)W(x,0)$ then the system may relax over time into a situation for which ((3)) holds.

In this note, we argue that for a free particle moving with constant p in one direction, $P(x,t) = \text{constant}$, but there is an underlying two dimensional wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$. We ascribe this to two x -probability distributions associated with motion. In particular: $v = (x_{\text{final}} - x_{\text{initial}}) / \Delta t$. If x_{final} and x_{initial} are both distributions such that on average $v = \text{constant}$, one needs to give a probability for both i.e. have two dimensions or an ordered pair. The two probability distributions, however, are not independent as they must describe a constant velocity i.e. all points of space being the same. This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ such that $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) = 1$. In other words, one may constrain two probability distributions to yield a deterministic type result for a single particle which appears as a probabilistic result for a steady stream. Born's Rule automatically applies to a free particle and is not a "postulate" as argued in (1). The form $\exp(ipx)$ follows from the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px$ we argue.

We further argue that if one creates a linear superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s i.e. $W(x) = \sum p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ then $\int dx W^*(x)W(x)$ is always linked to a steady stream probability picture i.e. $\sum p a^*(p)a(p) = 1$. This is why given a p , one does not know its x point- it is associated with a steady stream. As a result, we argue that there is always a meaning for Born's rule $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$. As a result $P(x,t=0) \neq W^*(x,t=0)W(x,t=0)$ must describe a probability which differs from the steady stream scenario linked with $\exp(ipx)$.

Determinism, Probability and a Free Particle

A particle moving in one direction with a constant p (momentum) (and velocity) is described by Newtonian mechanics through $x(t)$. " X " may be measured by an external ruler and t by an external clock. $x(t)$ is said to be a deterministic expression. One may ask: What is the probability for a particle to be at one x versus another? This question may be answered by giving the Δt the particle spends in each dx . If the particle, however, moves in only one direction, it seems that Δt is really a dynamic probability related to a single particle. $P(x) = \text{constant}$ may be associated with an ensemble of particles with constant p and moving in different directions, but with uniformly distributed different starting times i.e. a steady stream picture. Thus a $P(x)$ for a steady stream is the same as a dynamic probability Δt for a single particle. In other words stochasticity exists for the steady stream picture of many particles (or an ensemble) and not for the single particle. $P(x) = \text{constant}$ for a single particle means that dynamically each dx piece of space is considered the same because the particle spends the same time dt in each. This is not the same, it seems, as not knowing the result of throwing a die or tossing a coin.

The idea of all space points being the same or all dx the same, however, becomes more complicated if one proposes to replace the external ruler and clock with an internal one. In other words, one may argue that a particle itself measures space and time with a certain resolution. What is this resolution?

In one uses the Lorentz invariant:

$A = -Et + px$ ((4)) which is both the nonrelativistic and relativistic free particle action with $v=x/t$

then $t = \text{constant}/E$ and $x = \text{constant}/p$ maintain A constant. Photonic considerations lead to $\text{constant} = \hbar$. Thus there is a ruler with gradations \hbar/p . If one writes an eigenvalue equation:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

Then $\exp(ipx)$ automatically satisfies Born's rule:

$$\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1 \quad ((6))$$

1 as argued above suggests deterministic behaviour. $\exp(ipx)$ is two dimensional because both the starting and final point of the particle in a tiny time t are probabilistic so one needs an ordered pair (x_{initial} probability, x_{final} probability). These, however, cannot be independent because they must describe motion in one direction such that p is constant. $\exp(ipx)$, through Born's rule, gives this result. Thus double stochasticity with a constraint can give the appearance of determinism.

Single stochasticity cannot do this because a stochastic variable is automatically not deterministic. The two stochastic pieces $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ suggest that time within a wavelength \hbar/p does not really make sense, but makes sense on average (i.e. distances greater than a wavelength i.e. many wavelengths). Thus Born's rule is automatically associated with a free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$.

Interactions Through Impulse Hits

If one assumes that physical interactions occur through impulse hits based on momentum p , then a general wavefunction is:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((7))$$

This is no longer simply a mathematical Fourier series, but a description of the type of impulse hits which occur. One still has double stochasticity, but no longer $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$, but rather $\text{Real}(W(x))$ and $\text{Imaginary}(W(x))$. There is a new ruler gradation which is not constant. Even for a bound state for which the imaginary $W(x)$ pieces may cancel (for an even function), the physical impulse pieces, $\exp(ipx)$, still carry both distributions i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. It is only an averaging process which makes it appear as if the imaginary pieces of $W(x)$ are gone in a bound state.

$W^*(x)W(x)$ freezes out translation motion (just as in $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$). This leads to $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$ when integrated over x .

If one assumes as in (1) that $P(x,0) \neq W^*(x,0)W(x,0)$, then it seems that a quantum bound system would need to relax over some time period into:

$$P(x,t) = W^*(x,t)W(x,t) = W(x)W(x) \quad ((8))$$

This, however, seems to imply that the form ((7)) does not hold from the beginning, but if p based impulse hits are the means of interaction with a potential $V(x)$, it seems ((7)) should hold because this is ultimately linked with the steady stream picture associated with $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ when one integrates over dx .

We have argued that $P(x,t)$ describes an ensemble for the free particle case. Thus it should also represent an ensemble for the bound case as well. Thus it is not clear why $P(x,0)$ should not be equal to $W^*(x,0)W(x,0)$ for the single particle bound state.

We have argued that the Born rule $P(x,t)=W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ holds for a single free particle with constant p and motion in one direction and a single particle eigenstate. Thus it does not seem to be a postulate in these two cases. In (1), however, a $W(x,t) = \text{Sum over } n \text{ } b_n(t) W_n(x,t)$ situation is considered and so this should be examined, but first we consider the meaning of $W^*(x)W(x)$ integrated over dx .

Steady State Picture Associated with a Single Particle Bound State

We try to link a single particle bound wavefunction $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) \exp(ipx)$ to a steady stream scenario. We already argued that $\exp(ipx)$, describing a particle moving in one direction, maps into $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)=1$ because in a steady stream one may find the particle at any x with the same probability. This same set of $\exp(ipx)$ s constitute $W(x)$ and so even though $W(x)W(x)$ describes a function in x , $W^*(x)W(x)$ integrated over x collapses to the classical scenarios of various steady streams of particles with different momenta and weights i.e.

$$\text{Integral } dx \text{ } W^*(x)W(x) = \text{Integral } dx \text{ } \text{Sum over } p, p_1 \text{ } a^*(p_1)a(p) \exp(-ip_1x)\exp(ipx) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a^*(p)a(p). \quad ((9))$$

((9)) is no longer a bound particle picture, but a steady stream of constant p particles. This is why one may find a particular p at any x point, it seems. As a result, $W^*(x)W(x)$ has a very specific interpretation linked to a steady stream and this occurs already at the $\exp(ipx)$ level and also for any linear combination of $\exp(ipx)$ s, we argue.

Approach of (1) with $P(x,t=0) \neq W^*(x,0)W(x,0)$

In (1) several examples are given for $P(x,0) \neq W^*(x,0)W(x,0)$, including that of a quantum oscillator. Then:

$$W(x,t) = \sum_n b_n(t) W_n(x,t) \quad ((10))$$

$W(x,t)$ is not an eigenstate, but a solution of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. In particular, the following $W(x,t=0)$ is chosen:

$$W(x,t=0) = (B_0/(2 \cdot 3.14))^{1/2} \exp(-B_0 x^2/4 + i [A_0 x/2 + a_0]) \quad ((11))$$

For $t > 0$, $B_0 \rightarrow B(t)$, $A_0 \rightarrow A(t)$ and $a_0 \rightarrow a(t)$.

Inserting $W(x,t)$ into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation yields first order differential equations in d/dt linking $A(t)$, $B(t)$ and $a(t)$.

$P(x,t=0)$ is set equal to $\delta(x)$, but this is not the same as $W^*(x,t=0)W(x,t=0)$.

$P(x,t)$ is then said to satisfy:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } P(x,t) = d/dx \text{ partial } [-(2A(t) - B(t))x P(x,t)] + d/dx d/dx \text{ partial } P(x,t) \quad ((12))$$

A Gaussian is assumed for $P(x,t) = \text{sqrt}(C(t)/(2 \cdot 3.14)) \exp(-C(t)x^2/2)$ ((13))

and $C(t)$ linked to $A(t)$ and $B(t)$. It is then studied how $C(t)$ merges to $B(t)$.

For $t=0$, we argue that $W(x,0)$ may be written as:

$$W(x,0) = \sum_p a(p,t=0) \exp(ipx) \quad ((14))$$

Then $\int dx W^*(x,0)W(x,0)$ at $t=0$ should map into a steady stream probability scenario i.e.

$$\sum_p a^*(p)a(p) = 1 \quad ((15))$$

Thus we argue that $\int dx W^*(x,0)W(x,0)$ always has meaning through its link to a steady state probability scheme of variously weighted streams of particles with constant momentum. This should have a link with experiment as well because physical impulses occur with the free particle p 's. As a result, we argue that Born's rule $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ does not seem to be a postulate, but rather yields a steady stream type of probability when integrated over dx in all scenarios. Thus $P(x,t)$ in (1) must be something different from the steady stream "probability density" described by Born's rule which already exists for a free particle $\exp(ipx)$ and carries over into linear superpositions $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Born's rule $P(x,t) = W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ is not a postulate for a free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$. In particular, a free particle velocity is calculated using $(x_{\text{final}} - x_{\text{initial}}) / dt$, but x_{final} and x_{initial} may be governed by x -probability distributions. Thus both are stochastic and one may write an ordered pair $(P_1(x_{\text{initial}}), P_2(x_{\text{final}}))$. These two distributions, however, are constrained to yield a scenario which treats each x point as the same i.e. $P(x) = \text{constant}$. What does $P(x) = \text{constant}$ mean? For a single particle this does not seem to be a stochastic quantity, rather it applies to a steady stream of many particles. Then it describes the probability of hitting a particle at x .

The form $\exp(ipx)$ follows from the Lorentz invariant: Action = $-Et + px$ for a free particle i.e. from an eigenvalue equation: $-i d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. $\exp(ipx)$ automatically satisfies $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$ i.e. Born's rule, thus Born's rule is not a postulate, we argue. Rather it describes steady stream probability. As a result, we argue that this steady stream scenario carries over to linear superpositions of $\exp(ipx)$ s, i.e. $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$, which may be used as a solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equation for an energy eigenvalue.

For a general time-dependent solution $W(x,t=0)$, it is argued in (1) that $W^*(x,t=0)W(x,t=0)$ may not equal $P(x,t)$. We argue that $W(x,t=0)$ may be expanded as a linear superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s and so $W^*(x,t=0)W(x,t=0)$ should be guaranteed to have the steady stream interpretation (when integrated over dx) i.e. Born's rule should always apply. Thus the unintegrated form should also be physical. As a result, $P(x,t)$ used in (1) may represent something different from Born's rule result

References

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